

IMPROVING ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN THE ENGLISH SUBJECT OF GRADE 6 LEARNERS AT TANGWAY ELEMENTARY SCHOOL THROUGH EKEEP INTERVENTION

REYONNIE A. JUMARANG

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5678-5693>

revonnie.jumarang@deped.gov.ph

SDO Lipa City-Tangway Elementary School
Tangway, Lipa City, Batangas, Philippines

ABSTRACT

This study particularly addresses the difficulty of learners in grammar and sentence construction, which were remarkably noticed on submitted outputs during the first few months of implementing distance-learning modalities at Tangway Elementary School. The main goal is to document how to improve the academic performance in the English Subject of Grade 6 Learners at Tangway Elementary School during the school year 2020-2021. This study used a pretest and post-test design with the utilization of the teacher-constructed Self-Learning EKEEP Modules. Materials developed were designed both for online and modular platforms of learning. Parents as facilitators of learning were also guided on their roles in providing intervention. Outputs on EKEEP Modules were submitted on a weekly basis and evaluated attentively by the teacher to monitor learners' progress. Results obtained from the post-test were compared to the data gathered from the pretest and there was a significant improvement recorded in the learners' performance in grammar and sentence construction. The implementation of EKEEP Intervention for Grade 6 learners provided favorable outcomes that showed noteworthy progress on their academic performance in the English subject. This study was done at the time where distance-learning modalities are implemented at Tangway Elementary School. Active involvement of learner's parents and guardians play an important role in the success of the intervention program. What is less clear is if the same results will be obtained if there will be no household support available for targeted learners.

Keywords: English Grade-6, Grammar and Sentence Construction, Teaching and Learning, CALABARZON, Philippines